

CHANGING PERSPECTIVES IN INDIAN EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract:

Education is a unique asset for human beings to reach their goals in life. Through education any sort of knowledge that is gained can be put into practical basis and by practicing this in our day today life activities will help us to develop our knowledge and get experience. Earlier Gurukula system was one of the unique residential learning systems and here the Guru, the teacher will help his pupil's to acquire knowledge and get an eternal success in their life. In Gurukula the pupil's help their Guru in house core activities and also learn to lead their life in a positive manner as a down to earth learning is been taught to the pupils and as a gesture of respect shown to the Guru they give Gurudakshina at the end of their learning. After Gurukula we can observe the existence of British education policies and they introduced the circular learning system. After independence the government introduced the education is right to all and implemented a free and compulsory primary education to all. Later in education system many innovation and experiment has happened and they introduced an online base learning and teaching by the collaboration with other countries we can get our degree by online courses. The educationists thought that vocational learning is a best method of learning which helps the individual face the competition in this present world than curricular learning system. In present scenario we can observe the global partnership with various countries to get an education in various fields. The changing trends in education has made the people to gain knowledge through practical thinking and bring change in the society and is a part of nations development as Education is the only property that cannot be stolen by anyone.

Keywords: Education, System, Development, Vocational learning, trends in education and Knowledge.

1. INTRODUCTION

Education is a powerful asset which leads the individual to achieve their goals. In education system we can see tremendous changes as well as development from earlier to till modern century. In primitive time we can observe that giving education as well as getting education is treated as a very sacred aspect in each pupil's life. The objectives of the study are To understand the quality of education system in India. To sensitize the people to change their attitudes through the education system.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

According to Dr. C Chakrabarty; the knowledge, skills and productivity of our growing young and dynamic work force forms the backbone of our economy. To reap the benefits of such a young work force, need to implement the reforms in the education system and also bring forth new factors of production, namely knowledge, skills and technology which have the ability to unleash the productive frontiers of the economy in the most efficient and dynamic way. He further, underlines three major areas to be focused to ensure that our education system is sustainable and meets global standards: i. Quality of Education – in terms of infrastructure, teachers, accreditation, etc. ii. Affordability of Education – ensuring poor and deserving students are not denied education. iii. Ethics in Education – avoiding over-commercialization of education system. According to Dr. RadhikaKapur; In Indian education system, there has been growth taking place. Individuals from all areas and backgrounds are realizing the significance of education, there has been an increase in the enrolment of students in educational institutions and there have been advancements in the teaching-learning methods. On the other hand, the occurrences of problems prove to be impediments, which are required to get eliminated or modified. There should be formulation of appropriate measures and policies and their effective implementation would lead to development of the Indian education system.

According to Mrs. Mukesh Chahal; Higher education in India plays many roles. It is of extraordinary importance to many and reforms are often seen as significant threats to specific, social arrangements that provide benefits to powerful groups. Higher education in India is an extraordinarily important part of modern Indian society and it is intertwined in the political and social systems of the society. It is in need of change, development and important. In order to effectively plan for reforms and improvement, it is necessary to have in realistic perceptions of what is possible and what is not. According to Dr. R. N. Nadar, Indian education system is widely criticized in multi-dimensions for its failure to create required employability in its students according to the industry requirements and its inability to contribute to inclusive growth in the nation as a whole. The issues in the present education system that are daunting the growth of this country can be tackled effectively if constructive and committed actions are taken by the Government to resolve them.

In ancient India the Gurukula System is a residential learning system which had its own value and Gurukula system of learning is a holistic approach as in this system The Guru (Teacher) teaches his Shishyas (Pupil) the disciplined and cultured education which will help them to lead their life in a positive manner. In Gurukula, the Shishyas would help their Guru in the house chore activities which teaches them the simplicity and sharing of responsibilities and so on. After finishing their education pupil's offer Gurudakshina, the one-time fees to their Guru as a token of gratitude. In Ancient India the many famous Kings and rulers built many Universities for higher education like Nalanda University, was one of the famous ancient university built by one of the Gupta emperor named Kumara Gupta. Then there were various other universities like Takshashila, Vikramashila, Valabhi, Somapura and so on. These universities motivated the students to learn more about Indian culture, tradition and involve these in their life. But in India the caste system became one of the cruel aspects specially in getting education in Indian society. Here the people divided them based on their classes and the caste was been upheld and demotivated the lower caste people and these did not get an opportunity to learn from the Gurukula's and Universities this made major change in the system of education as it was been given only to the elites and poor low caste people were

been ignored. Later, when British entered into India they introduced the new type of learning system that is class room teaching and curricular system of learning. In this system, the student and teacher relationship had become commercial in nature as the payment was made in monetary basis this type of learning system made the individuals to learn the different cultures of different countries and here the British's gave more importance to learn the English language. British East India company they had no concern about empowerment in education system in India, their prime goal was to improve their trade and marketing in the country and making a good profit by using education as a weapon; British education system encouraged the pupil to do new innovation in technology as well as they also did the publicity related to their work. British introduced the new educational policies which helped them to gain more from our country.

After independence our government introduced right to education for all. Government made the compulsory and free education for children up to 14 years. But it did not become a success; later, another mile stone of education system in India was the recommendations of national education policy by Kottari Committee. The main objectives of National educational policy were to provide equal educational opportunities for all. To Promote research and technology, to empower advanced agricultural technology the new pattern of education, three language formula, introduction of regional language in higher education, development of agricultural and industrial education and adult education. To combat the changing socio-economic needs of the country, Government of India announced a new National Policy on Education in 1986. Universalisation of primary education, vocationalisation of secondary education and specialisation of higher education were the main features of this policy. The basic recommendations of the policy were related to national form of education, more emphasis on learning, delinking degree for any service, vocationalisation of education, importance on moral values, emphasis on reforms in the examination system, education of the weaker section of the society, starting of an All India Educational Service, starting of Open Universities, establishing many Navodaya Vidyalayas, women education, Operation Blackboard and preservation of culture. Primary education – been free and compulsory. Mid-day meal has been started in schools since 1995 to control the drop-out rate.

The School learning process also changed its teaching methods like Nali Kali, Saturdays No bag Day was to encourage children to learn creative and innovatively engage in the learning process. In higher education system to improve the quality of education the University Grant Commission was introduced in the Central level and drafted new education policy as it sees to the education qualification of the teaching professionals through the competitive exams, granted funds for workshops, seminar, conferences and so on to enhance the knowledge and skills among the pupils and educators. There is a tremendous change in the education system as the degree could be received through online courses. In present trend, the online education has been a blessing for the people who can avail this type of learning and add on to their academics and improve in their career status. It is where they can learn in their leisure time and get a validated certificate. A numerous field is been explored to the general public as there is a global partnership with various countries to get an education in these various fields. Here, the pupils can enrol themselves in these courses which is of their interest based study at their fingertips and enhance knowledge as well as they can get their refresher course, faculty development programmes which is feasible through this online learning. The Indian Government has introduced numerous skill based education for the pupils and also have allocated funds in the annual budget for the same. Here, the pupils get the skill through the experts and also the job placements. If they want to start their own business they can pitch

their ideas and get the fund through government to become an entrepreneur. The education system has been changed through imbibing knowledge and wisdom to vocational training and making a place of their own in the society being independent.

3. CONCLUSION

The changing trend in education through many innovation and experiment has made the people to gain knowledge through practical thinking and bring change in the society and is a part of nation's development. Education is the only property that cannot be stolen by anyone.

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